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Website

Deliverable 5.3

H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020 PHYMOT

Physics of Microbial Motility

Project Name	PHYMOT
Grant Agreement Number	955910
Coordinator	Gerhard Gompper
Author	Gerrit Vliegenthart
Email	etn-phymot@fz-juelich.de
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1. Introduction

PHYMOTs communication strategy includes the website as an important tool to increase the visibility of the network. The implementation and maintenance of the website is the responsibility of the project coordinator located at Forschungszentrum Jülich.

Website objectives

- 1) Present the PHYMOT consortium to the outside world
- 2) Disseminate and communicate PHYMOT events, activities, and project outcomes to a wider audience
- 3) Download medium for (open) project templates, providing links to information concerning H2020 for both PIs and ESRs

2. Website construction and operation

The PHYMOT website is developed and maintained in WordPress and available at <https://etn-phymot.eu>. The website is physically hosted at a server at Forschungszentrum Jülich. The site is regularly maintained and updated by the manager of the network. As from the website launch in early December 2020, the site's functionality is continuously adapted to accommodate changing needs. As of January 2022, the ESRs actively participate in maintaining the website and adding new functionalities.

3. Structure of the website

The website contains a main or home page that states the mission of PHYMOT. From the menu bar on top there is access to the following pages:

Home: Mission of PHYMOT

Network: Here all beneficiaries and partners have space to present their institute and the people involved in their project.

Research: All PHYMOT projects briefly explain their project objectives on this page

Jobs: PHYMOT open positions are advertised here

Internal: This page contains links to other websites that might be of interest to PHYNOT members, it provides links to EU training documents regarding H2020-ITNs and it provides links to PHYMOT templates.

Contact: This section provides contact information of the PHYNOT coordinator and manager

Events: On this page, PHYMOT events are announced and meeting details (program, venue, travel) are shared here.